

Subaltern Identity in *Purple Hibiscus*: The Impact of Domestic Violence and Cultural Conflict

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Abstract

Many African nations continue to suffer from severe problems related to the spiritual, cultural, emotional, and intellectual wounds inflicted by colonizers. The status of women is becoming increasingly insecure due to the “Subaltern East” and restrictive societal conditions, as illustrated in Chimamanda Ngozi Adichie’s novel *Purple Hibiscus*. Post-colonial and psycho-social theories are employed to evaluate the marginalization and mistreatment of women. The paper analyses gender-based violence, specifically domestic abuse, in *Purple Hibiscus*. It delineates the intricate influence of colonial systems, religion, patriarchal ideals, politics, and tradition in instigating disputes and perpetuating female subjection and exploitation, as well as domestic violence and the subaltern identity of the “double exploited.”

Introduction

The postcolonial term “subaltern” refers to the oppressed groups. In that instance, the subalterns in Chimamanda Ngozi Adichie’s *Purple Hibiscus* are more oppressed than the title would suggest. The violence against women, Christian religious interference, cultural conflicts, colonial powers, and gender discrimination because of patriarchal dominance are all criticized in the book. Simultaneously, it prompts more critiques of African Igbo culture via several people whose perspectives illustrate diverse possibilities for establishing a more secure world—or, at the very least, a secular era that ensures safety for women. Numerous Nigerian women authors, including Ayobami Adebayo, Lola Shoneyin, Akwaeke Emezi, Sefi Atta, Yejide Kilanko, Chinelo Okparanta, and Chimamanda Ngozi Adichie, expose readers to a variety of tales about women’s traumas, misfortunes, and sorrows. Even though their characters are imaginary, the issues they portray are a mirror of historical pain and societal oppression. According to Aidoo

(1996) intellectuals, activists, creative writers, and women writers arouse human consciousness in addition to depicting the pathetic situation of female subalterns. The novel’s portrayal of women’s subjugation and fight for rights is retrieved using post-colonial and modern psycho-social theories. Domestic violence, dehumanization, physical and psychological abuse, societal constraints, religious taboos, political repression, patriarchal control, and physical assault are all part of the lives of many Nigerian women. Women are indeed subalterns in this regard.

Purple Hibiscus criticizes the colonial powers that continue to oppress subalterns. In Nigerian society, oppressed women face numerous challenges, which are depicted in *Purple Hibiscus* in a flawless and fairly modern manner. Domestic violence and cultural inequality, characterized by the devaluation of individuals to an unequivocally subordinate identity of “other,” constitute the principal source of all material, social, and political injustices. Gender and violence are intricately connected. Ilika et al. (2002) in clinical study of 300 women in eastern Nigeria found that 40% had experienced violence in the preceding 12 months (54). When reading Adichie’s book *The Purple Hibiscus*, one is confronted with such startling figures of female violence and human depravity.

The novel’s first sentence makes clear that gender inequality and demanding patriarchal forces exist outside of their households at the state level. A dehumanized and oppressed community is mostly made up of cultural contacts and supremacy. Many Africans’ identities are suppressed and manipulated by the patriarchal norms of their culture and power-based interactions, particularly when it comes to the elite social dominance and the dominance of the African patriarchal system. These two social identities perpetrate oppression and horrors against family

members domestically, resulting in a conflation of exploitation. Male dominance resulting from the power supremacy of invaders and their religion can be explained by a detailed investigation of the domination, subjugation, brutality, and exploitation (Frantz et al., 1995). Franc's arguments claim that the colonial system included harsh punishment, legal changes, power imbalances, and hypocrisy. As portrayed in *Purple Hibiscus*, Fanon's rudimentary paradigm is most properly regarded by many as a phenomenology of oppression or ethnic conflict.

Majority of Nigerian women face the possibility of mistreatment and trauma from circumstances such as Boko Haram Syndrome, skewed social expectations, and cultural norms, a lack of social facilities and social support, and marital abuse. In addition to the typical brutal surroundings and incidents, many Nigerian women have experienced sexual abuse, displacement, and—above all—psychological trauma and agonizing mental agony because of the present Boko Haram crisis. A multitude of women and youth perished and suffered turmoil due to rivalry, abuses of authority, and a series of terrorist incidents. Professor Cathy Caruth said it was quite painful to see or experience these horrible things. The traumatic and broken lives of numerous female Boko Haram survivors are revealed in reports. In the news item “Nigerian Women Rescued from Boko Haram Face Trauma and Stigma,” Michelle Faul, the CTV News affiliate, described the circumstances surrounding women who were rescued from Boko Haram as “traumatizing and horrifying.”

It is important to recognize the underlying contradictions in both Igbo culture and Christianity while acknowledging the actual issue depicted in the book. The taboos for women imposed by the focus and values placed on “Kola nut” in the social and cultural life of the Igbo people in Nigeria prior to colonization are reflected in the Igbo cultural and ceremonial government in Nigeri. The position that social organizations ceremoniously bestowed upon women is symbolized by the restriction of the privilege to crack open the sacred Kola nut, which is revered by the Igbo people. Despite the absence of a substantial conceptual foundation for these perspectives, aside from the assertion that Igbo culture had Hebrew origins, it suggests her societal inequality.

Around the world, women and children have histor-

ically been the victims of domestic violence. Gender-based domestic abuse is one of the most common social injustices that Nigerian women face. *Purple Hibiscus* discusses the reasons why women require greater protection and care. Religion and cultural impact are two elements that contribute to domestic violence against African women, particularly in Nigeria.

Chimamanda Ngozi Adichie keeps an eye on the customs of other well-known Nigerian authors, such as Chinua Achebe. In the context of twentieth-century Nigeria, authors address current social and cultural issues and conflicts. In addition to addressing other issues in their novels, several authors, including Nobel laureate Nardine Gordimer Nawal el Sadaawi, Ama Ata Aidoo, Buchi Emecheta, Flora Nwapa, Bessie Head, and more recent arrivals to the literary scene, such as Seffi Attah, Akachi Adimora Ezeigbo, and Chimamanda Adiche have explored gender issues from a female perspective.

In order to comprehend how gender and violence manifest in gender relations, several African scholars have recently started incorporating these ideas into gender studies (Lindsay & Miescher, 2003, p.1-3). Additionally, rather of continuing in previous disruptive roles, women novelists find alternative ways to make their views heard and expose social inequalities in their works. One such initiative is the *Purple Hibiscus*.

Patriarchal subordination and colonial dominance

Patriarchal subjugation and colonial control are two sides of the same coin. Patriarchism represents the male impetus to dominate feminine identity, whereas colonialism reflects a compulsion to invade and possess territories. Ann McClintock describes male travel as “erotic of ravishment.” Adichie's *Purple Hibiscus* demonstrates the interconnection between colonialism, the patriarchal system, and Christianity, highlighting how conventional conventions undermine the uncomplicated lives of certain innocent women. The history of colonialism illustrates how male explorers trespassed onto uncharted territories. Supremacy is upheld through the rigidity, stubbornness, and dominance of the ideology and expectations placed on subordinates or the subjugated. The colonial worldview of superiority that still perme-

ates Africans' daily lives centuries after colonialism is the reason behind Father Benedict's insistence on conducting prayers only in Latin rather than their native Igbo language.

It is horrifying to see how these worldviews are permeating Nigerians' daily lives. Several social ills can be brought on by the current male dominance and female inferiority. Physical violence, spousal abuse, female infanticide, rape and female circumcision are prevalent social afflictions. As a "colonial product," Papa Eugene carries on the civilized man's lineage. To establish his dominance, supremacy, and arrogance, he treats even those closest to him poorly and adopts the mindset of the colonizers through his extreme dedication to Catholicism. He imparts knowledge of the Christian theological concept of sin and redemption to family members in the name of culture and religion. Charles E. Bressler claims that postcolonial theory explores the social, political, and economic issues of both the colonizer and the colonized, going beyond the confines of conventional literary studies. In order to assess ethnic conflicts, cultural conflicts, subaltern marginalization, and abuse of women, an investigation grounded in 21st Century Post-colonial theory that aggressively critiques the current ideas and beliefs regarding race and imperialism will be equally helpful (Bressler, 2012).

Eugene epitomizes colonialism and the challenges it poses for subsequent generations. In her essay "Adichie's Genealogies: National and Feminine Novels," Andrade makes the case that *Purple Hibiscus* tells the story of a country while also symbolizing family politics. As a result, *Purple Hibiscus* delves deeply into many aspects of modern life. Andrade (2011, p. 91), further, notes that Adichie's examination of the current political turmoil in Nigeria is shown through the book's illustrations of cross-continental inspirations and interests.

A lot of papa's beliefs derive from patriarchal ideals and the colonial system. Papa asserts that an effective school must possess a formidable, impenetrable wall to safeguard the students and, naturally, uphold regulations. Once in church, Mama and Kambili are not permitted to expose their legs and are expected to cover their hair. Since Papa believes it is wrong for women to display their hair in public, he be-

comes enraged whenever he sees her scarf slide away. While Ifemo's children are free, talkative, and happy around their logical, thinking mother, Jaja and Kambili dwell in fearful silence under Papa, who represents patriarchal tyranny.

Mama Beatrice whispers all the time. Because she is aware of the consequences of even the smallest mistakes on her side, Kambili's mother takes care to keep things discreet and respectable. Ifeoma values freedom over wealth and is proud of her independence. Kambili's small mind has always been wrecked by Papa's physical abuse and usual patriarchal tyranny, and she perceives everything save the things that are listed in Papa's calendar as sins. Jaja and Kambili's life have suffered psychologically as a result. Her interpersonal relationships suffer because of her quiet separation from friends and family. Kambili adheres to the "scheduled" life that her patriarchal father set down for the kids on paper to win his acceptance and gratitude. Nevertheless, it always leaves her feeling depressed and confined.

In her examination of racist folklore and contemporary literature, Walker highlighted the dual colonization of Black women and their subordinate position in patriarchal African civilizations. He asserts that Black women are termed "the mule of the world" in folklore, a designation that aptly reflects their social status, since they bear the loads that others have declined to shoulder (Walker & Parmar, 1996 p. 237). Adichie eloquently illustrates how or ideology can be either oppressive or helpful depending on how we approach it—by contrasting Papa and Father Benedict's inflexible, dogmatic ideas of faith with Aunt Ifeoma's liberal, happy attitude toward children. The two siblings' divergent philosophies based on how they view the father. Adichie skilfully contrasts this viewpoint; Ifemo's deep love and devotion for her father, particularly during his illness and when he required assistance, is contrasted with Papa's irate and evil treatment of his father, Papa Nnukwe, as "a heathen." Eugene's Christian mindset and colonial supremacy led him to forbid his father from entering his mansion. Papa Nnukwu is upset: "... look at me. Even though my son possesses a mansion big enough to accommodate every man in Abba, I frequently find myself without anything to eat. Those missionaries should not have been allowed to follow him" (*Purple Hibiscus*, p.83).

How deeply ingrained is papa's inflexibility? Kambili's mental state as she grieves over her grandfather reflects her religious beliefs. She is depressed and in mourning, yet she can't get rid of the idea that she is doing sin. She is also concerned that her father will be upset with her for disobeying him. Ifeoma's children's unrestrained grief for Papa Nnukwe contrasts once more with Papa's mockery and contempt for his "heathen" father.

Papa was a typical product of the colonists and the missionary school. Papa was disciplined by the missionary school priests for his transgression. Since Kambili was previously trained by harsh punishments, Papa now wishes to prevent him from sinning in the traditional Catholic manner. Another indication of the continuous colonization is the Catholic practice of formally confirming Christian children as Catholics by giving them an English name. In her dream, Kambili also links Nigerian political oppression with household tyranny.

The convergence of these societal systems in female captivity, abuse, domestic violence, and misery is particularly pronounced in the narrative of this post-colonial novel. Women have been disenfranchised as subalterns by patriarchal cultures that are ingrained in Nigerian social traditions and reinforced by colonial male rule. Women suffer from physical and mental oppression as a result.

Domestic violence

Slavery has been abolished in Nigeria, and colonizers have departed the country. However, patriarchal ideals and the indigenous cum Christian religious values provided no place for women's self-awareness, growth, or development. Both colonialism and the substituted patriarchal institutions, which were nourished by colonial religious dogmas and superiority ideals, were detrimental to both genders. It is merely a new manifestation of patriarchy that is actively oppressing women. However, the ugly forms of aggression, dominance, and abuse of power continue to exist both inside and outside of the family, which is a microcosm of society.

Through the novel's symbolic use of "figurines," Adichie envisions the continuous parade of chaos and suffering and how it destroys many people's identities. Papa Eugene threw the prayer book at Jaja

when he refused to partake in the communion. The harsh penalties are an expression of his affection and a strong man's method of guiding his wife and kids. Part of the exploding aggression that intensifies in the home is breaking the figurines.

Kambili recalls how her mother painstakingly polished the figurines, particularly after Papa Eugene had physically assaulted her. Every time Papa feels they are straying from his authority; he removes his belt and hits them all:

Papa was like a Fulani nomad—as he swung his belt at Mama, Jaja, and me muttering that the devil will not win. We did not move two steps away from the leather belt that swished through the air." (*Purple Hibiscus*, p.102).

It is regrettable that Papa's conviction on sin and punishment is so deeply rooted in his subconscious that he asserts women and children need endure these punishments to progress appropriately. To absolve Kambili of her sins, Papa splashes her feet with hot, scorching water. Papa Eugene had started to mistreat Jaja as well. Eugene fractured Jaja's little finger as a disciplinary measure for not achieving first place in the Holy Communion class. Mama arrives to inform Kambili and Jaja that Papa broke a table on her stomach while they are at Nnukwe's residence. Papa's brutal physical abuse and assault are the only reasons she keeps missing carriages.

Social stigmas were used to subjugate women by patriarchal regimes and traditional native values. One powerful way to oppress and devalue female identities is through physical assault and domestic violence. At the height of the political cycle of oppression, violence, and tyranny, papa's personal tyranny was demonstrated at home when Mama turned down Papa's desire to see Father Benedict. She became like a bleeding gunny bag as Eugene beat her behind the closed doors of their bedroom.

We watched Papa come down from the landing. Like the jute rice bags his factory workers imported in bulk at the same border, Mama was slung over his shoulders: "

There's blood on the floor," Jaja remarked. We cleaned up the trickle of blood that ran off like someone carrying a leaking painting jar all the way downstairs. "I'll get the brush from the bathroom." (*Purple Hibiscus*, p. 33)

Another time, Kambili's face is slapped by the father.

Papa Nnukwu was enraged due to Kambili and Jaja's conceit in bringing his painting. Her fragile body was curled on the floor, bleeding, while he persistently kicked her with his metal-buckled shoes while shouting. As she lay on the floor between the torn remnants of her grandfather's photograph, suffering from internal bleeding and a cracked rib, he had nearly beaten her to death.

In a way, the figurines serve as a euphemism for domestic abuse and the patriarch Papa Eugene's façade. Father Benedict in the church consistently extols him as a paragon of virtue, and he is both prosperous and esteemed. The fragmented figure, conversely, serves as a comedic representation of the patriarch masquerading as Papa Eugene. It's no surprise that Adichie portrays a powerful, moderately affluent man in the role of a stereotypically malevolent, traditional patriarch. It makes sense to think of the countless women and children who have been subjected to abuse by ignorant, superstitious individuals from lower socioeconomic classes. The empirical studies on physical abuse carried out in Nigeria provide evidence of marital violence, as evidenced by the works of several African American women novelists.

Psychological impact of domestic abuse on women

Women who experience physical attack suffer psychological effects from domestic abuse. Young children's minds are impacted by the force of such crimes that their parents perpetrate in front of them in their own homes. Kambili is trapped in her early years. Kambili endures more psychological suffering than bodily harm because of her father's ongoing physical abuse. In addition to being psychologically damaged by her father's abuse of her mother, she covertly desires her father's death. She disapproves of her mother's submissive demeanour and occasionally inquires why she does not protect her children from their detrimental father. Kimbili, unable to mature in a serene environment, enforces silence and quietly observes a tumultuous world. This could be the cause of her cousin Amaka's perception of them as "abnormal," leading her to question her mother about Kambili and Jaja, asking whether "something is not right with them."

Kambili is mentally damaged by Papa's harsh and

controlling personality, which is typical of a patriarch. She believes that everything is sinful except for things that are not on Papa's schedule. It has hindered her own development psychologically. Naturally, her quiet prevents her from socializing, enjoying herself, and savouring the pleasure of relationships. Due to her lack of connections, Kambili became depressed and lonely despite her constant attempts to win her patriarchal father's acceptance and gratitude.

Subaltern identity: submitting to patriarchal ideals and subservience

The *Purple Hibiscus* uses Adichie's fictional universe to illustrate the essential causes of domestic violence against women. One of the causes of the underlying aggression may be docility or accepting one's fate. Kambili and Jaja are also victims of domestic oppression, much like Mama. The God-like father character in Kambili's early mind raises the question of whether this is the standard subconscious male image that every child has, which eventually transforms into docility and a purposeful devotion to patriarchal values. Kambili and Mama consider it a positive. The family's speculation on Mama Beatrice's inability to bear additional children, coupled with their suggestion to marry a new wife for procreation, exemplifies mental abuse and domestic violence prevalent globally.

The family members are subjected to mental tyrannies that control every aspect of their existence in addition to physical assaults on their mother. One illustration of the lack of freedom is affixed on the wall and always carried by the children. It specifies the times for everything, even "family time." One form of oppression that might hinder human growth in all areas of life is censorship. Ade Coke doesn't know that his boss's family is being abused. He notes the incongruity between Papa's private life and his convictions, his treatment of his children, and his need for absolute compliance from his family. While Jaja eventually gets over her shame about disobeying Papa's orders, Kambili holds on to her guilt. For Kambili to be happy, she always yearned for her father's approval and works hard in class to win her father's approval. It is difficult to break free from such thoughts, which are reflections of the bondage. Mama is in agreement. Because she lives a dependent life, she puts up with violence, abuse, and torment on a regular basis.

Developing forward-thinking ideas

To what extent was Adichie able to develop positive female characters? Some of her characters serve as examples of how not everyone is suffering; there is hope. Like other African women writers, Adichie endeavours to reframe women in more advantageous roles, distancing them from their marginalized circumstances. All their pieces illustrate gender-based violence.

The fresh route to liberation is opened by Aunt Ifeoma. Ifeoma disrupts Kambili's structured, compliant existence and introduces Kambili and Jaja to a novel sense of autonomy and interpersonal engagement. She encourages others to express their opinions and is fearless and liberal. Ifeoma has a flexible worldview and interpersonal interactions but lacks inflexible norms and dogmas. She is accused of being a riot supporter, and the authorities search her residence. At last, she is fired by the authorities. Aunt Ifeoma is strict and morally upright despite this.

The character descriptions of Kambili and Amaka illustrate how their disparate upbringings either strengthen or weaken. Kambili lives in a personal cocoon characterized by uncertainty, concern, anxiety, and impotence, whereas Amaka, of the same age, is notably articulate, self-assured, and culturally astute. Since she has acquired the "art of silent crying," Kambili is even frightened to cry. Nevertheless, her cousin Amaka declines to assign an English name to her daughter, viewing this as her means of resisting contemporary colonialism and authoritarian oppression.

As a result, *Purple Hibiscus* is special because it goes beyond dehumanization and oppression. The book promotes stopping family members from oppressing one another at home. It encourages readers to think about certain societal issues and instils an egalitarian/feminist awareness to fight for one's identity.

Jaja's symbolic journey towards freedom is represented by his planting of purple hibiscus. By isolating herself from routine contacts, Kambili is constrained in her silence and subjected to Papa's interpretation of immorality. Aunt Ifeoma embodies the contemporary Nigerian woman—progressive, open-

minded, and engaging. Ifeoma assists Kambili in breaking her quiet and speaking up rather than keeping to herself. Aunt Ifeoma is the one who helps Jaja become self-sufficient and free. His Nsukka freedom is symbolized by a few stalks of purple hibiscus, which Ifeoma brought home as a present from Nsukka. Jaja gradually starts to show his independence. Unfortunately, violence and brutality impose censorship and compliance, and anything that deviates from that is brutally destroyed, as demonstrated by the murder of campaigner Ade Coker.

Combating violence needs considerable courage and vigour, and when limits are transgressed, aggression may provoke retaliatory violence, as exemplified by Mama Beatrice. When Beatrice could no longer stand Papa Eugene's physical abuse and aggression, she makes the heinous decision to poison him to ruin him. There are a lot of important problems raised by Mama's violent claim to freedom. Homicide cannot resolve domestic difficulties. These extreme options, however, underscore a distinct facet of Mama's internal turmoil as a victim and her profound pain, which rendered her devoid of alternative means to escape Papa's crimes.

The allusion to the defiant leader who resisted British rule symbolizes the quest for personal freedom and independence. Ifeoma wants Jaja to rebel against authority, much like the Opobo Jaja did. In the end, Kambili, Papa's dutiful child, also turns against her father after he cruelly beats her. Kambili suddenly loses her fury due to her father's maltreatment after Eugene injures her internal organs, leaving her in a hospital bed with fractured ribs and internal haemorrhaging. Moreover, Papa is no longer the divinity Kambili previously revered.

Although the phrase "empowerment of women" is frequently used, its actual implementation and overall successes are not as well-known. The end of violence, freedom of choice, financial stability, and, of course, access to education is all necessary for subaltern women to be empowered. This is succeeded by a segment of infrastructure advancement and political representation. This study has elucidated the fundamental causes of domestic violence against women as depicted in Adichie's fictional realm.

Ifeoma's struggle for rights and the political turmoil both at the individual and national levels, culture

starts the healing process. Adichie adds the background political unrest in addition to the family's shift or metamorphosis. Papa Eugene calls Ade Coker to confirm the latest coup in Nigeria, which foreshadows how "men would always overthrow one another." Through a sight Kambili sees outside the car window, Adichie presents violence outside:

She seemed to want to keep us from seeing the woman and the soldiers. I witnessed a woman spitting at a soldier as we rushed by, and the soldier brandished a whip. It was a lengthy whip. Before landing on the woman's shoulder, it coiled in midair. Another soldier was laughing, kicking down fruit tables, and using his boots to squish papayas (*Purple Hibiscus* P.44).

Kambili is not quite conscious of the political connotations that are developing in the nation. However, the purple hibiscus flowered in Jaja's yard, and references are made to the "scent of freedom." Adichie is able to allude to Nigeria's political climate and the way that violence, in any form, always affects the country's women and children by comparing it to the cries of the irate mobs.

The shattering of figurines signifies the impending end of the family's legacy of violence. Jaja has commenced his rebellion against his father's biased beliefs by refusing to partake in communion, the destruction of figurines disrupts the household dynamic, and the mother no longer fears physical violence. Jaja's silence or refusal to communicate in English exemplifies the escalating tension and insurrection inside the domestic sphere against the previously prevailing patriarchal authority and domestic violence.

Jaja's interaction with the purple hibiscus, evoking a sense of enchantment, symbolizes his connection to authentic freedom, tranquility, and the joy that Aunt Ifeoma invoked in her morning prayers. Adichie effectively conveys the lesson Kambili derived from the aroma of the purple hibiscus that Jaja had cultivated in Ifeoma's garden: "freedom to be, to do." With the support of Aunt Ifeoma and Father Amadi, Kambili gradually emerges from her shell. In both political and national contexts, as well as inside familial relationships, the purple hibiscus in Aunt Ifeoma's garden symbolizes a novel fragrance of liberty and autonomy.

Conclusion

Cultural conflicts, interpersonal violence, sexual assault, and Adichie's strong desire to raise awareness of human suffering are all reflected in *Purple Hibiscus*. She uses vivid language to portray authentic characters on an imaginary canvas. Her adept manipulation of words and literary devices animates the pace and tone of the event. Adichie skilfully employs the political coup as a backdrop to illustrate the power struggle and the subjugation of women like Beatrice, Ifeoma, and Kambili. Ethnic tensions and cultural conflicts are widespread in *Purple Hibiscus*, and they have even erupted within academic institutions. Political upheaval, religious dominance, patriarchal power dominance inside the household, and the potential for female servitude are also depicted.

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